

ISSUES OF DEVELOPING THE ORGANIZATION OF INNOVATIVE BANKING SERVICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. This thesis examines the issues of developing the organization of innovative banking services in commercial banks. As a result of the analysis, the main problems were identified, including the stability of technological infrastructure, the identification system, the low level of diversification of innovative products, the weak integration of artificial intelligence, and staffing provision.

Keywords: innovative banking services, digital banking, artificial intelligence, remote banking services, fintech, financial technologies.

Introduction. The 21st century is a period of rapid development of information technologies, during which concepts such as “artificial intelligence,” “digital technologies,” and the “Internet of Things” are being widely implemented in practice. In the banking system, the transition from the traditional service delivery model to the model of providing services through digital platforms is accelerating.

The “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, approved by Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, defined the tasks of creating conveniences for customers in the provision of banking services and improving remote banking services. From this point of view, the issues of developing the organization of innovative banking services in commercial banks are considered relevant.

The purpose of the study is to develop scientific proposals and practical recommendations for improving the organization of innovative banking services in commercial banks.

Analysis and Results. Such rapid growth in the number of remote users imposes two types of strategic responsibility on commercial banks: first, ensuring the technical stability and cybersecurity of the system; second, offering personalized innovative services to customers through the analysis of large volumes of data, namely Big Data.

Table 1.1 – Analytical Information on Payments Made Through the Instant Payment System of the Central Bank¹

¹www.cbu.uz – Information from the official website of the Central Bank.

No.	Bank name	Payments received during March 2026:		Including to the budget: amount, billion soums	
		Number	Amount, billion soums	Number	Amount, billion soums
1	Central Bank	872,044	18,977	-	-
2	National Bank	345,758	16,743	117,737	3,390
3	Uzsanoatqurilishbank	273,174	11,154	81,950	3,783
4	Agrobank	19,000	1,266	1,360	47
5	Mikrokreditbank	83,722	2,066	24,856	152
6	Xalq Bank	247,410	12,285	92,189	327
7	Garant Bank	36,337	2,010	12,024	48
8	BRB	51,516	354	36,339	157
9	Hamkorbank	290,707	6,419	78,810	694
10	Asaka Bank	75,516	8,637	12,297	1,995
11	Ipak Yo'li Bank	26,960	2,478	1,391	68
12	Trastbank	114,052	4,951	22,227	479,406
13	Aloqabank	1,856,809	5,412	1,612,111	2,769
14	Ipoteka-bank	27,536	1,164	2,377	71
15	KDB Bank Uzbekistan	1,764	296	248	30
16	Soderot Bank	16988	196	3,078	4
17	Universal Bank	45,257	1,938	10,004	94
18	Kapitalbank	40,162	21,602	3,127	271
19	Asia Alliance Bank	96,317	4,559	17,831	315
20	Orient Finans Bank	103,494	5,475	18,354	391
21	TBC Bank	739,328	2,927	2,741	34
22	Anor Bank	5,632	571	706	231
23	Uzum Bank	188,566	339	78,684	72
24	Other banks	51,090	3,345	3,653	455.36
25	Central Securities Depository, AVO	-	-	-	-
	Total:	5,609,139	135,169	2,234,094	15,752

According to the analytical data, during March of the current year alone, among the commercial banks that carried out the largest number of payment operations, Aloqabank performed 1,856,809 payments amounting to 5,412.00 billion soums, TBC Bank performed 739,328 payments amounting to 2,927 billion

soums, the National Bank performed 345,758 payments amounting to 16,743 billion soums, Hamkorbank performed 290,707 payments amounting to 6,419 billion soums, Uzsanoatqurilishbank performed 273,174 payments amounting to 11,154 billion soums, and Xalq Bank performed 247,410 payment operations amounting to 12,285 billion soums.

These are only payments made through bank cash desks, mobile banking applications, and online banking platforms. In addition, many individuals also make payments through payment providers such as “Payme,” “Click,” “Click Evolution,” and “Oson.” This indicates that today the population’s demand for payment services is increasing day by day.

Competition among banking platforms in Uzbekistan is now taking place not only in terms of interest rates, but also in terms of the number and diversity of services. The expansion of the range of services in banking applications contributes to the growth of customer data and, as a result, to the creation of “hyper-personalized” banking products.

The results of the analysis show that banks operating on the basis of a fully digital model, such as TBC Bank and Anor Bank, demonstrate higher results in terms of the growth rates of their credit and deposit portfolios compared to traditional or hybrid banks. This situation is explained by the operational efficiency of digital platforms, lower costs, and the ability to provide prompt service to customers.

The analysis of the table data shows that, as of March 2026, the struggle for digital leadership in the banking services market of Uzbekistan has become intense. TBC Bank, with 97.27 points, Anor Bank, with 94.46 points, and Bank Ipak Yo’li, with 94.02 points, occupied the highest positions in the ranking and recorded an “(uz) AAA” indicator, which represents an ideal level, thereby setting benchmarks in the field of mobile banking.

Although the analyses show that the technological gap between traditional banks and digital banks is decreasing, imbalances are still observed in the ratings on the Google Play and App Store platforms. For example, in institutions such as Mikrokreditbank and Ipoteka-bank, the rating of Android users is significantly higher than that of iOS users, which indicates the need to optimize applications equally for different operating systems.

Table 1.2 – Ratings of Bank Mobile Applications as of March 2026²

²Standard and sensitive ratings – <https://sunattagayev-cloud.github.io/Bank-apps-rating/>

Bank	Googl e Play	App Stor e	Activit y	Final score	Rating	Descriptio n
TBC Bank	97.5	96.4	96.8	97.27	(uz) AAA	Exemplary
Anor Bank	94.5	80.7	95.8	94.46	(uz) AAA	Exemplary
Bank Ipak Yo'li	91.2	98.5	95.2	94.02	(uz) AAA	Exemplary
Uzum Bank	89.7	95.6	95.3	91.51	(uz) AA	Almost exemplary
Aloqabank	87.8	91	93.8	88.87	(uz) AA	Almost exemplary
Tenge Bank	86	89.9	92.8	87.66	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Asakabank	86	85.6	92.6	86.57	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Uzsanoatqurilishba nk	85.3	86.9	92.8	86.38	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
National Bank of Uzbekistan	85.2	85.9	92.9	86.11	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Open Bank	81.9	89.2	92.3	85.36	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Kapitalbank	83.3	81.2	92.2	83.87	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Xalq Bank	82.4	72.9	93.3	83.24	(uz) A	Almost exemplary
Mikrokreditbank	79.9	65.7	91.4	80.93	(uz) BBB	Very good
Trastbank	78.6	80.8	91	80.27	(uz) BBB	Very good
Asia Alliance Bank	79.3	63.5	90.7	80.23	(uz) BBB	Very good
AVO Bank	78.4	70.4	92.6	79.2	(uz) BBB	Very good
BRB	62.1	83.8	90.6	78.88	(uz) BBB	Very good
Agrobank	74	84	92.2	77.97	(uz) BBB	Very good
Turonbank	75.2	74.8	90.2	76.68	(uz) BBB	Very good
Octobank	72.8	78.1	90.6	75.37	(uz) BB	Better
Infinbank	71.3	70.8	91.4	73.32	(uz) BB	Better
Hamkorbank	71.6	68.4	91.3	73.24	(uz) BB	Better
Hayot Bank	69.5	71.2	88.2	71.39	(uz) BB	Better
KDB Bank Uzbekistan	69.7	56.4	86.2	70.06	(uz) BB	Better

Apex Bank	66.9	69.3	88.6	69.49	(uz) B	Good
Ipoteka-bank	67.5	51.2	91.6	69.07	(uz) B	Good
Davr-bank	65.5	68.7	90.2	68.41	(uz) B	Good
Universal Bank	63	56.6	88.6	64.96	(uz) B	Good
Garant Bank	57.4	62.8	86.7	60.47	(uz) CCC	Almost good

The average score of all applications was 79.84.

The fact that user activity in banking applications is above 90 percent in almost all banks indicates that customers have fully adapted to remote services. However, for banks at the lower end of the ranking, such as Garant Bank, with 60.47 points, and Universal Bank, with 64.96 points, technical upgrades and the improvement of customer experience, namely UX, remain urgent tasks in order to maintain competitiveness. In general, the quality of a bank’s mobile application is currently considered a key strategic resource that ensures customer loyalty.

Conclusion. Although significant achievements have been made in the organization of innovative banking services in commercial banks of Uzbekistan, cases of technological and operational lagging still remain in some banks. By improving the quality of bank mobile applications, optimizing them equally for different operating systems, and introducing “hyper-personalized” services, it is possible to further increase the competitiveness of banks.

References:

1. Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy.
2. www.cbu.uz – Data from the official website of the Central Bank.
3. Standard and sensitive ratings data – <https://sunattagayev-cloud.github.io/Bank-apps-rating/>

